

The Reactivity of the Chlorine Atom in the Benzene Nucleus.

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The reactivity of the halogen atom in a benzene nucleus under the influence of the nitro and other negative groups, has for a long time engaged the attention of chemists. It has been known that the nitro group is the only group that, in the absence of other groups causes really pronounced activation of the halogen atom, and that in comparison with the halogen in a halogeno-mononitrobenzene, *e.g.*, *o*-chloronitrobenzene, the halogen in other halogeno-monosubstituted benzenes, *e.g.*, *o*-chlorocyanobenzene and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, is practically inert. It would thus be understood why it is advantageous, for a proper comparison of the effects of substituents on the replacement of the halogen in an aromatic nucleus, to select such compounds as contain necessarily a nitro group in addition to the halogen atom and the activating substituent.

The object of the present investigation has been mainly the determination of the relative influence of (a) the nitro, (b) the cyano, and (c) the carboxyl groups on the reactivity of a chlorine atom adjacent to each of these groups in an aromatic nucleus. Attention has, therefore, been directed chiefly towards the condensations of (i) 1-chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene, (ii) 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene, and (iii) 1-chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoic acid (2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid), all of which contain a nitro group in addition to the activating substituent, with the following compounds: aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, diethylamine, urea, sodium ethoxide, sodium methoxide and the sodium derivatives of ethyl malonate, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl cyanoacetate, nitromethane and cyanoacetamide. Although several of these condensations have necessarily involved repetitions of previous work, the methods of experiment have often been modified with considerable advantage, and the results have helped in drawing certain clear and definite conclusions regarding the reactivity of the chlorine atom when it has either a nitro, a cyano or a carboxyl group adjacent to it and a further nitro group always fixed in the *para* position.

The condensation of 1-chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene with aniline and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines has now been effected by merely warming a mixture of the components on the water-bath for 10-15 minutes in the case of aniline and about half an hour in the case of the toluidines (*vide* Reitzenstein, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, *ii*, 68, 251), the yields being practically quantitative.

Schöpf (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3440), who prepared 2:4-dinitrodiphenylamine by heating 1-bromo-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene and aniline to boiling for a long time, observed that under these conditions complications often set in, leading to the formation of nitroanilinobenzamide and nitroanilinobenzanilide. Again, Baudet (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1924, 43, 707) prepared 2-cyano-4-nitrodiphenylamine by mixing chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene and aniline in alcohol and heating under pressure in a sealed tube at 150° for 5 hours, no condensation being observed to take place on heating at a lower temperature, *e.g.*, 130° for 2½ hours.

It is found *now* that the condensation between chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene and aniline is most quickly and conveniently effected by heating the substances together at 180°; the reaction is completed within ¾-1 hour and an excellent yield of 2-cyano-4-nitrodiphenylamine is obtained. Not only is the reaction completed in a much shorter time, but it is also kept well under control and does not permit the occurrence of any side-reactions. The same method has been successfully applied in the case of the toluidines also. The condensation, however, takes place only with *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*-toluidine not condensing with chlorocyanonitrobenzene even on heating at 200° for 2 hours (*cf.* Baudet, *loc. cit.*).

It may, therefore, be regarded as definitely established that the reactivity of the chlorine, at least with respect to primary aromatic amines, is less marked in chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene than in chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene. Thus, whereas Mattaar (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1922, 41, 24, 103) succeeded in effecting the condensation between chloro-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene and aniline by refluxing in alcohol for 1 hour, chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene is now found to react only on heating with aniline to 180° for about an hour, the same being the case with *m*- and *p*-toluidines. Again, chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene could not be condensed at all with *o*-toluidine and methylaniline even on heating for several hours at 200°, while Mattaar found the condensation of these two bases with chloro-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene to be easily accomplished. These observations, therefore, are of consider-

able value in explaining the remarkable effect of exchanging the position of the two groups, *viz.*, cyano and nitro in chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene on the reactivity of the halogen.

The effect of the carboxyl group in the *ortho* position is shown by the fact that the condensation of 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid with aniline and the toluidines takes place with greater ease than in the case of chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene. The reaction is completed in the case of aniline and *m*- and *p*-toluidines by heating the reacting substances at 140° for 20-30 minutes, *o*-toluidine alone requiring to be heated to a somewhat higher temperature (160°) (*cf.* Locher, *Annalen*, 1894, 279, 275; also Kahn, *ibid.*, p. 270).

It may be concluded as a result of these experiments that the activating influence of the nitro, the cyano and the carboxyl groups on the replacement of halogen by means of the aromatic amines decreases in the order: nitro > carboxyl > cyano.

In this connection, attempts have also been made to condense chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene with the chloroanilines and the nitroanilines. The method employed has been to heat the substances at 190—200° for an hour or two. Of the three chloroanilines it is found that only *p*-chloroaniline condenses with chlorocyanonitrobenzene, giving 2-cyano-4-nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine (m. p. 282°). None of the nitroanilines could, however, be condensed with chlorocyanonitrobenzene. These observations serve admirably to illustrate the relative influence of a negative substituent, *e. g.*, Cl or NO₂, in different positions in the aniline molecule in reducing the basicity and activity of the NH₂ group.

Diethylamine reacts very readily with chlorodinitrobenzene, the condensation taking place when the components are refluxed in alcohol for 20—30 minutes. The extreme ease with which the reaction takes place is also observed by Romburgh (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1883, 2, 40) in the case of 1-bromo-2:4-dinitrobenzene. The condensation between diethylamine and chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene is also similarly accomplished by mixing the components in alcohol and boiling under reflux for 2—3 hours. In the case of 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid, however, reaction does not take place even on boiling for 4—5 hours. No better results are obtained by employing the sodium salt or the methyl ester of the acid for the condensation.

The reactivity of the halogen in these compounds towards urea has also been studied with interesting results. When chloro-2:4-

dinitrobenzene and urea are fused together 2:4-dinitroaniline is obtained. This method, for the replacement of the Cl by the NH_2 group, is not, however, of general applicability, for such replacement does not occur with *o*-, *m*- or *p*-chloronitrobenzene.

The reaction proceeds on somewhat different lines in the case of chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene. When this compound is similarly heated with urea, a product is obtained melting at 190° . It is not 2-cyano-4-nitroaniline, m. p. 209° , (which has been prepared by Baudet by heating chlorocyanonitrobenzene with alcoholic ammonia under pressure), for it is not soluble in dilute or strong hydrochloric acid and can not be acetylated, whereby the absence of the NH_2 group is proved. The product could not be hydrolysed by boiling with strong HCl, nor even by digesting with concentrated H_2SO_4 at 100° , which renders the presence of a CN group doubtful. Analysis points to the probability of the compound being 2-uramido-5-nitrobenzamide. This constitution receives further support from the observation that the product of hydrolysis with moderately strong potash (15%) yields an acid (m. p. 264°), which is found to be identical with 5-nitroanthranilic acid (m. p. 263°) which has been prepared for comparison by direct nitration of anthranilic acid (the NH_2 group protected by acetylation) with fuming nitric acid (*cf.* Rupe, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1097).

On hydrolysis by vigorous boiling with strong potash (20%) the product obtained is 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m.p. 229°) the NH_2 group of the 5-nitroanthranilic acid being substituted by hydroxyl, thus:

The formation of 2:4-dinitroaniline from 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene and urea is now readily explained on the basis of the extreme reactivity of the halogen, which would appear to have easily been acted upon by the ammonia evolved from the urea. On the other hand; the lesser reactivity of chlorocyanonitrobenzene (1:2:4) would render such a replacement of chlorine with ammonia difficult, so that on prolonged heating the urea itself enters the molecule.

No definite product could, however, be isolated by condensing 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid or its methyl ester with urea, the major portion of the acid or ester being recovered unchanged.

With sodium ethoxide and sodium methoxide, again, chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene condenses with extreme ease, the reaction being completed by refluxing for 20—30 minutes (cf. Cahours, *Annalen*, 1849, 69, 236; 1850, 74, 315; Willgerodt, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 763; also Maikopar, *ibid.*, 1873, 6, 564).

The condensation between chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene and sodium ethoxide and methoxide is similarly effected by refluxing for 1-2 hours with sodium dissolved in the absolute alcohol, the products being identified with 1-ethoxy- and 1-methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene which had been obtained previously by Blanksma from 1-ethoxy- and 1-methoxy-2-amino-4-nitrobenzene respectively, by diazotisation and treatment with potassium cuprocyanide (*Chem. Weekblad*, 1908, 5, 789).

On similarly refluxing 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid, as well as its sodium salt, with sodium ethoxide and methoxide for 4-5 hours, the reaction does not proceed at all and most of the acid is recovered unchanged.

Thus, it has been found that with regard to these reagents as well as with diethylamine and urea, the halogen in chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene, while although less reactive than in chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene, is replaced far more readily than that in 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid: the order with these reagents being $\text{NO}_2 \succ \text{CN} > \text{COOH}$.

From the foregoing experiments, therefore, the conclusion seems inevitable that, just as the order in which the different halogens are replaced depends upon the reagent used, as shown by the experiments of Luloffs (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1901, 20, 292) and Rheinlander (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3099), even so is the relative activating influence of the various negative groups on the halogen atom in an aromatic nucleus dependent largely on the nature of the reagents which are employed for substitution.

Again, if the results of the quantitative experiments of Mattaar and Baudet (*loc. cit.*) be taken into consideration, it must be conceded that with sodium ethoxide and methoxide, chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene reacts far more readily than chloro-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene, whereas the reverse is found to be the case with the aromatic amines. This furnishes, therefore, a further illustration of the rule that the

nature of the particular reagent employed largely governs the relative influence of the activating substituents on the halogen atom.

Attention may in this connection be drawn to two interesting observations which seem to receive an explanation from this peculiarity. It has been found that sodium ethoxide reacts far more readily with *p*-nitrochlorobenzene than with *o*-nitrochlorobenzene and this observation is in line with that made by Rheinlander (*loc. cit.*), namely, that the speed of the reaction of sodium ethoxide with *p*-bromonitrobenzene is twice as great as that with *o*-bromonitrobenzene. The greater reactivity towards this reagent of chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene than of chloro-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene appears thus to be readily explained as being due to the relative positions of the nitro group in these two compounds.

With regard to the reactivity of these substituted halogenated nitrobenzenes towards β -ketonic esters and allied derivatives, reference might be made to the work of Richter (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2470), Reissert and Heiler (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4364), Borsche (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 602) and Borsche, Stackmann and Makaroff-Semljanski (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 2222) who have condensed sodioacetoacetic and sodiomalonic esters with substituted halogenated nitrobenzenes. This has now been extended to the study of the condensation of 1-chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene and 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid with the sodium derivatives of not only ethyl malonate and ethyl acetoacetate but also of ethyl cyanoacetate, nitromethane and cyanoacetamide. It is found, however, that reaction takes place only in the following cases: (a) chlorodinitrobenzene with sodiomalonic and sodioacetoacetic esters, (b) chlorodinitrobenzene and chlorocyanonitrobenzene with sodium cyanoacetamide. Even the use of catalysts like copper dust and copper acetate has not been found to bring about any reaction in the other cases.

The observations of Borsche, Stackmann and Makaroff-Semljanski (*loc. cit.*) are hereby corroborated. Thus, whereas these authors have condensed 1-bromo-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene with sodiomalonic and sodioacetoacetic esters, it is now found that 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene does not react with these esters, although repeated attempts have been made under different conditions to bring these into reaction. This difference in the behaviour of halogeno-2-nitro-4-cyanobenzene and of halogeno-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene towards these reagents as well as towards the aromatic amines (*vide*

supra) serves, therefore, as one more example of the superior influence of the nitro group when adjacent to the halogen atom.

The condensations of chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene and chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene with sodium cyanoacetamide have yielded very interesting results which are reserved for a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene.—To 40 c.c. fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.5), well cooled in ice, *o*-chlorocyanobenzene (10 g.) (Montague, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1900, 19, 50) was gradually added with shaking. To the clear brown solution at 0° conc. H_2SO_4 (40 c.c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. After standing an hour in the ice-bath, the liquid was poured into crushed ice, the precipitate collected, washed with 50% alcohol and crystallised from boiling alcohol as shining straw-yellow needles, m.p. 106°, yield 12-13 g. (*cf.* Borsche, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 664).

4-Chloro-3-cyanoaniline.—To concentrated HCl (15-20 c.c.) in a small long-necked flask granular tin (8 g.) was added and the whole heated on a wire-gauze. When the evolution of hydrogen had become vigorous, chlorocyanonitrobenzene (3 g.) was gradually added with shaking, and the mixture boiled down to three-fourths the volume (15-20 minutes). On cooling, the clear yellow solution deposited a crystalline mass of the stannichloride. The mixture was diluted with a little water, made strongly alkaline with 50% caustic soda and directly extracted with ether. The product, obtained by evaporating the ether, crystallised from absolute alcohol in almost white needles, m.p. 133°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 18.45. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 18.38 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by warming 4-chloro-3-cyanoaniline (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (3-4 c.c.) to complete solution (10 minutes) and pouring into water; it crystallised from alcohol in small white needles, m.p. 190°, yield 1 g. (Found: N, 14.37. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 14.41 per cent).

4-Chloro-3-cyanoaniline could not be hydrolysed by strong H_2SO_4 or HCl, the sulphate (m.p. 200.2°) or the hydrochloride (m.p. 224-26°) of the amine being the only products formed. Even on boiling with aqueous or alcoholic potash the substance remained unchanged.

2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid (*cf.* Rupe, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1099).—Crude *o*-chlorobenzoic acid (Kodak's technical, 20 g.) was slowly

treated with strong H_2SO_4 (40 c.c.) when HCl fumes were given off and the solid slowly dissolved. Nitric acid (d 1.4, 20 c.c.) was gradually added to this solution, cooled under the tap, with shaking and another 10 c.c. conc. H_2SO_4 added. It was warmed on the water-bath for an hour, cooled and poured into cold water (500 c.c.). The precipitate crystallised from boiling water as white prisms, m.p. 164° , yield 10-12 g.

The methyl ester was obtained by saturating with dry HCl at the ordinary temperature a solution of the acid (10 g.) in dry methyl alcohol (30 c.c.). The hot solution was cooled and again saturated with HCl gas and on leaving for 4 hours, the ester separated almost completely. The crystals were washed with 30 c.c. water and 5 c.c. N-NaOH . 10 G. of the pure ester (m.p. 72°) were obtained.

CONDENSATIONS WITH AROMATIC AMINES.

A. Chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene.

(i) *With aniline: 2:4-dinitrodiphenylamine.*—(a) A mixture of chlorodinitrobenzene (2 g.) and a slight excess of aniline (1.1 g.) was heated on the water-bath (10-15 minutes). The mixture was then dumped into cold water, the excess of aniline removed by washing with dilute HCl and the product crystallised from alcohol as shining orange needles, m.p. 158° , yield about 2.5 g.

(b) Chlorodinitrobenzene (2 g.) was gradually added with shaking to aniline (1.5 g.) when cooling was produced and a clear red liquid resulted. After allowing to stand for an hour, the mixture was worked up in the usual way, m.p. $157-58^\circ$, yield 2.3 g.

(ii) *With o-, m- and p-toluidines.*—The condensation of chlorodinitrobenzene (2 g.) with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidine (1.3 g.) was effected as above by warming on the water-bath for half an hour. The products obtained in the usual way were crystallised from glacial acetic acid: 2:4-dinitrophenyl-*o*-tolylamine (m.p. 118°), 2:4-dinitrophenyl-*m*-tolylamine (m.p. 160°) and 2:4-dinitrophenyl-*p*-tolylamine (m.p. 135°) were obtained.

B. Chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene.

(i) *With aniline: 2-cyano-4-nitrodiphenylamine.*—A mixture of chlorocyanonitrobenzene (2 g.) and aniline (1.5 g., about $1\frac{1}{2}$ mols.) was heated at 180° for $\frac{3}{4}$ -1 hour. The clear dark-red liquid solidified on cooling and was freed from excess of aniline in the usual way

by triturating with very dilute HCl. The product crystallised from alcohol in clusters of lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 171°, yield 2. g. (Found: N, 17.76. $C_{13}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.57 per cent).

(ii) *With p-toluidine: 2-cyano-4-nitro-4'-methyldiphenylamine.*—The condensation was effected in precisely the same manner as in the case of aniline by heating the mixture of chlorocyanonitrobenzene (2 g.) and *p*-toluidine (1.8 g.) in an oil-bath at 180-85° for an hour. The product, worked up as usual, crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining yellow needles, m.p. 217°, yield 1.7 g. (Found: N, 16.93. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.60 per cent).

(iii) *With m-toluidine: 2-cyano-4-nitro-3'-methyldiphenylamine.*—On repeating the experiment with *m*-toluidine exactly as in the previous case, 1.5 g. of the product, crystallising from alcohol in small pale green crystals, m.p. 140°, are obtained. (Found: N, 16.78. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.60 per cent).

(iv) *With o-toluidine and methylaniline.*—The above experiment was done with *o*-toluidine and methylaniline, but there was no condensation, the chlorocyanonitrobenzene being recovered unchanged in each case. No better results were obtained even when the components were heated at 200° for 2 hours.

(v) *With p-chloroaniline: 2-cyano-4-nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine.*—The mixture of chlorocyanonitrobenzene (2 g.) and *p*-chloroaniline (1.9 g.) was similarly heated at 190-195° for 1 hour. The product, after treatment in the usual manner, crystallised from acetic acid in bright yellow needles (1.1 g.), m.p. 282°. (Found: N, 15.52. $C_{13}H_8O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 15.35 per cent).

C. 2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic Acid.

(i) *With aniline: 2-anilino-5-nitrobenzoic acid.*—2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid (2 g.) and aniline (1.4 g.) were heated together at 140° for 20 minutes. The product was washed with dilute HCl and crystallised from acetic acid as pale yellow needles, m.p. 250°. (cf. Schopff, *loc. cit.*)

2-Anilino-5-nitrobenzamide.—2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzamide (2 g.) and aniline (1.4 g.) were heated together at 160° for half an hour. The product, purified in the usual manner, was crystallised from alcohol in shining yellowish-green needles, m.p. 190°, yield 1.7 g. (Found: N, 16.59. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent).

Methyl 2-anilido-5-nitrobenzoate.—Methyl 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoate (2 g.) and aniline (1.4 g.) were heated together at 160° for 10-15 minutes. On cooling, the mixture solidified to a sludge of crystals, which became granular on stirring for a while with 40 c.c. *N*-HCl. This was taken in a mortar, powdered with a little methyl alcohol and 2*N*-NaOH (1 c.c.) added drop by drop, when the whole thing was transformed into a mass of golden yellow crystals. The product crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow flat needles, m.p. 100°, yield 1.6 g. (Found : N, 10.46. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.29 per cent).

(ii) *With o-toluidine : 5-nitro-2-o-toluidinobenzoic acid*, (cf. Locher, *loc. cit.*) obtained in the usual way by heating together chloronitrobenzoic acid (2 g.) and *o*-toluidine (1.6 g.) at 160° for about half an hour, crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 254°.

(iii) *With p-toluidine : 5-nitro-2-p-toluidinobenzoic acid*, (cf. Kahn, *loc. cit.*) obtained by heating the components at 140° for 20 minutes, melted at 262°.

(iv) *With m-toluidine : 5-nitro-2-m-toluidinobenzoic acid*, prepared exactly as in the above case, crystallised from acetic acid in bright yellow needles, m. p. 256°, yield about 1.8 g. from 2 g. of chloronitrobenzoic acid. (Found : N, 10.52. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.29 per cent).

CONDENSATIONS WITH DIETHYLAMINE.

2:4-Dinitrodiethylaniline.—To a solution of chlorodinitrobenzene (2 g.) in ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.) diethylamine (1 g.) was added and the solution refluxed on the water-bath for 20-30 minutes. On concentrating, the product crystallised out, m.p. 81°, yield 1.2 g. Romburgh (*loc. cit.*) obtained this product by leaving an alcoholic mixture of 1-bromo-2:4-dinitrobenzene and diethylamine undisturbed for several hours.

2-Cyano-4-nitrodiethylaniline.—Chlorocyanonitrobenzene (2 g.) was similarly boiled under reflux with diethylamine (1.2 g.) in absolute ethyl alcohol for 2-3 hours. The solution was concentrated and poured into water and the product crystallised from absolute alcohol in fine pale-yellow needles, m. p. 88°, yield 1.4 g. (Found : N, 19.41. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19.18 per cent).

CONDENSATIONS WITH UREA.

2:4-Dinitroaniline.—Chlorodinitrobenzene (3 g.) was added in small quantities to molten urea (3 g.) at 160° with stirring. After heating for an hour the contents of the flask, when quite cold, were washed 3 or 4 times with warm water to remove excess of urea and the product crystallised from boiling water as bright yellow needles, m. p. 176°, yield about 2 g. (Found: N, 23.28. $C_6H_5O_4N_3$ requires N, 22.95 per cent).

2-Uramido-5-nitrobenzamide.—Chlorocyanonitrobenzene (3 g.) and urea (3 g.) were similarly heated together at 165-170° for 2 hours. After washing with warm water, the product was extracted with acetone and the substance, obtained on evaporating acetone, crystallised from boiling water in small orange-yellow needles, m. p. 198°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 25.35. $C_8H_8O_4N_4$ requires N, 25.0 per cent).

2-Uramido-5-nitrobenzamide (5 g.) was heated with caustic potash (15%, 10-15 c.c.) just to boiling for half an hour, when ammonia was evolved. The clear liquid was acidified and the precipitate, after washing with a little hot water, crystallised from aqueous alcohol in golden-yellow needles, m. p. 264°. The product was identified with 5-nitroanthranilic acid prepared by the following method which was found to be more convenient and gave a purer product than that of Rupe (*loc. cit.*) who employed a mixture of nitric acid and sulphuric acids for the nitration. Acetyl anthranilic acid (1 g.) was added gradually to fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.5, 5 c.c.) with constant cooling. The clear liquid, after leaving for half an hour, was poured into water and the precipitate of 5-nitroacetyl anthranilic acid (m. p. 214°) was deacetylated by boiling with concentrated HCl for half an hour and the 5-nitroanthranilic acid crystallised from aqueous alcohol in shining yellow needles, m. p. 263°.

Hydrolysis of 2-uramido-5-nitrobenzamide by vigorous boiling with 20% caustic potash yielded 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m.p. 229°). *O*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzene did not react with urea.

CONDENSATIONS WITH SODIUM ETHOXIDE AND METHOXIDE.

1-Ethoxy-2:4-dinitrobenzene (m.p. 86°) and *1-methoxy-2:4-dinitrobenzene* (m. p. 89°), (*cf.* Willgerodt, *loc. cit.*, Maikopar, *loc. cit.*)

were obtained by refluxing chlorodinitrobenzene (2 g.) with sodium (0.25 g.) dissolved in absolute ethyl and methyl alcohol respectively for 20-30 minutes.

1-Ethoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene (m.p. 101°) and 1-methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene (m.p. 128°) (*vide* Baudet, *loc. cit.*) were obtained when chlorocyanonitrobenzene (1.8 g.) was added to sodium (0.25 g.) dissolved in absolute ethyl and methyl alcohol respectively and refluxed for 1-2 hours. They were recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. (Found: N, 14.51. $C_9H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent). (Found: N, 15.8. $C_8H_6O_3N_2$ requires N, 15.73 per cent). No reaction was found to take place when chloronitrobenzoic acid (either the free acid or the sodium salt) was similarly refluxed with sodium dissolved in absolute ethyl and methyl alcohol respectively for 4-5 hours, the unchanged acid being recovered in each case.

On condensing sodium ethoxide and *p*-chloronitrobenzene exactly as in the previous cases, the reaction proceeded normally with the formation of *p*-nitrophenetole, m.p. 57°. A by-product was also formed which melted at 154° and was identified with *pp'*-dichloro-azoxybenzene.

No definite product could, however, be isolated on repeating the experiment with *o*-chloronitrobenzene.

Condensations with Sodiomalonic Ester, Sodio-acetoacetic Ester, etc.

2:4-Dinitrophenylmalonic ester (m.p. 52°) and 2:4-dinitrophenyl acetoacetic ester (m.p. 83°) (*cf.* Reissert and Heller, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 4364) were obtained by adding chlorodinitrobenzene to a solution of ethyl malonate and ethyl acetoacetate (2 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. sodium) and refluxing for 2-3 hours. The products were crystallised from alcohol.